

COALITION OF AGRICULTURE IN AMBIANCE AMENDMENT

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is a pressing global issue that is affecting various sectors, and agriculture is no exception. The impact of climate change on agriculture is wide-ranging and poses significant challenges to food security, livelihoods, and the overall sustainability of agricultural practices. In this essay, we will explore the various ways climate change affects agriculture and the measures that can be taken to mitigate its adverse effects. One of the most significant impacts of climate change on agriculture is the alteration of weather patterns. Extreme weather events such as floods, droughts, heat waves, and hurricanes have become more frequent and intense. These events can damage crops, destroy infrastructure, and disrupt supply chains, leading to food shortages and price fluctuations. Moreover, unpredictable weather patterns make it difficult for farmers to plan their planting and harvesting schedules, affecting crop yields and productivity. Rising temperatures are another major consequence of climate change that affects agriculture. Higher temperatures can lead to the depletion of soil moisture, increased evaporation, and heat stress on plants and livestock. Many crops have specific temperature requirements for optimal growth, and exceeding these thresholds can lead to reduced yields and lower crop quality.

KEYWORDS: Climate, Drought, Crop Yield, Green House Gas, Livestock, Supply Chain

INTRODUCTION:

Climate change refers to long term shifts in temperature and weather patterns. This happens due to many internal and external factors mostly to the augment the level of atmospheric CO₂ produced by the use of fossil fuels, deforestation, burning crop residual, release of methane gas from rice field, power generation, and damage to biodiversity etc. Climate is a primary determinant of agriculture productivity. Change in climate expected to influence crop and livestock production, hydrologic balances, input supplies and other component of agriculture system (Ndaki.; 2016). As greenhouse gas emission in the atmosphere is increasing, the temperature is also increasing due to greenhouse effect. The average global temperature is increasing continuously and is expected to rise by two degrees Celsius until 2100 which would cause substantial economic losses at global level. The raise in temperature which leads to higher respiration rate, shorter period of seed formation and hence lowers down the biomass production. Climate change changes the incidence and distribution of pest and pathogens, increase rate of soil erosion and degradation, increasing tropospheric ozone level due to rise in temperature. The negative impact of higher temperature on reproduction can lead to reduced pollen production, viability, and pollen tube growth, with a resulting decrease in seed yield. Climate change also affects the microbial population and their enzymatic activities in soil .livestock can be affected by climate change by affecting the quality and amount of forage from grassland, decreasing in milk yield, heat stress and metabolic disorder, immune suppression, and other dairy operation.

There are two main strategies to reduce the impact of climate change i.e., adaptation and mitigation. Adaptation is the process of adjusting to the current and future aspects of climate change. Mitigation is the making the impact of climate change less severe by preventing or reducing the emission greenhouse gases into atmosphere. To control climate change start afforestation, stop using products which release CFCs to stop global warming and ozone depletion, accelerate energy efficiently and renewable energy use. Climate change leads to

squat production of agriculture commodities leading to loss of economy and GDP of the country. Climate change is a “social dilemma” which has ill effects on human, plants animals and on our mother earth therefore; we must take precautionary measures to protect our environment.

Livestock may also suffer from heat stress, reducing their productivity and increasing the risk of diseases. Changes in precipitation patterns are also a concern. Some regions may experience more intense rainfall, leading to soil erosion, nutrient runoff, and water logging. In contrast, others may face prolonged periods of drought, resulting in water scarcity for irrigation and livestock. In both cases, agricultural productivity is adversely affected, and farmers face challenges in managing water resources efficiently. Additionally, climate change is altering the distribution and prevalence of pests and diseases. Warmer temperatures and changing precipitation patterns create more favorable conditions for certain pests to thrive, leading to outbreaks that can devastate crops and reduce yields. Similarly, warmer winters may fail to kill off certain pests, allowing them to survive and cause damage in subsequent seasons. New disease vectors may also emerge, posing risks to both crops and livestock. The impact of climate change on agriculture is not limited to crop production but extends to the broader agricultural value chain. Changes in crop yields and quality can affect food processing industries and lead to price fluctuations for consumers. Moreover, disruptions in the supply chain caused by extreme weather events can result in post-harvest losses and food wastage, exacerbating the food security challenges faced by vulnerable communities. To address the impact of climate change on agriculture, various adaptation and mitigation strategies can be employed. Promoting sustainable agricultural practices is crucial. This includes the adoption of climate-resilient crop varieties, crop rotation, agroforestry, and the conservation of water resources through efficient irrigation techniques. Precision agriculture, which utilizes technology to optimize resource use and monitor crop health, can also play a significant role in mitigating climate change’s adverse effects.

Another essential aspect is improving climate information and early warning systems to help farmers anticipate and prepare for extreme weather

er events. Access to weather forecasts and advisory services can enable farmers to make informed decisions about planting, irrigation, and pest control, reducing their vulnerability to climate-related risks. Furthermore, policymakers must invest in rural infrastructure, such as water storage facilities, roads, and markets, to enhance the resilience of agricultural communities. Financial support and insurance schemes can provide a safety net for farmers in the face of climate-related losses, encouraging them to adopt climate-smart practices.

GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS

Agriculture is a substantial source of greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to global warming and climate change (Charles et al.;2013). The primary greenhouse gases associated with agricultural activities include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O). Here's how agriculture contributes to each of these gases:

a. Methane (CH₄): Methane is produced in agricultural activities such as enteric fermentation in livestock (belching), manure management, and rice cultivation. Livestock, particularly ruminant animals like cattle and sheep, have specialized digestive systems that produce methane as a byproduct of digestion. Manure management practices, such as storage and decomposition, also release methane.

b. Nitrous Oxide (N₂O): Nitrous oxide is released from agricultural activities related to nitrogen use, such as synthetic fertilizers, manure application, and crop residues. These practices can lead to the release of nitrous oxide through a process called nitrification and denitrification.

c. Carbon Dioxide (CO₂): Agricultural practices contribute to carbon dioxide emissions through deforestation for agriculture expansion, land-use changes, and the burning of agricultural residues.

DEFORESTATION AND LAND-USE CHANGE:

Deforestation for agricultural expansion is a significant driver of greenhouse gas emissions. Forests act as carbon sinks, absorbing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. When forests are cleared for agriculture, the stored carbon is released back into the atmosphere, contributing to global warming. Furthermore, the conversion of natural habitats into agricultural land reduces biodiversity and disrupts ecosystems, leading to ecological imbalances.

VULNERABILITY TO CLIMATE IMPACTS

While agriculture is a contributor to climate change, it is also highly vulnerable to the impacts of a changing climate. Here are some of the ways in which agriculture is affected (Liwenga et al; 2013).

a. Changing Weather Patterns: Climate change has led to shifts in weather patterns, including changes in precipitation, temperature, and the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events. These alterations can affect crop yields, water availability for irrigation, and livestock health.

b. Water Scarcity: Changes in precipitation patterns and increasing temperatures can lead to water scarcity, making it challenging for farmers to access sufficient water for irrigation and livestock.

c. Crop and Livestock Vulnerability: Rising temperatures and changing weather patterns can affect crop growth and the timing of plant development. Heat stress can reduce crop yields, and changing rainfall patterns can impact crop water requirements. Additionally, livestock may face health issues due to heat stress and an increase in pests and diseases.

d. Pests and Diseases: Climate change can alter the distribution and prevalence of pests and diseases, affecting crop and livestock health. New disease vectors may emerge, posing risks to food security and agricultural productivity.

e. Soil Erosion and Degradation: Extreme weather events, such as heavy rainfall and droughts, can contribute to soil erosion and degradation, reducing soil fertility and agricultural productivity.

MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION STRATEGIES:

To address agriculture's role in climate change and enhance its resilience to climate impacts, various mitigation and adaptation strategies can be employed:

a. Climate-Smart Agriculture: Implementing climate-smart agricultural practices, such as agroforestry, conservation agriculture, and integrated pest management, can reduce greenhouse gas emissions while enhancing productivity and resilience (Nyasiimi et al.; 2020).

b. Sustainable Land Use: Promoting sustainable land-use practices, such as reforestation, afforestation, and agroecology, can help sequester carbon and mitigate the impact of deforestation.

c. Improved Livestock Management: Sustainable livestock management practices, such as better feed-

ing strategies, methane-reducing additives, and improved manure management, can help reduce methane emissions from livestock.

d. Efficient Water Management: Implementing efficient irrigation techniques, rainwater harvesting, and water-efficient crop varieties can help address water scarcity challenges in agriculture.

e. Diversification of Crops and Livestock: Diversifying crops and livestock breeds can enhance agricultural resilience to climate change by reducing reliance on a single commodity and making the system more adaptable to changing conditions.

f. Early Warning Systems: Investing in weather forecasting and early warning systems can help farmers anticipate and prepare for extreme weather events, reducing the risk of crop losses and other climate-related damages.

g. Research and Innovation: Continued research and innovation in agriculture are essential to develop climate-resilient crop varieties, improve farming techniques, and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

The Effects of drought, heat waves, flooding, an increase in pests and plant diseases, and decreased food yields and nutritional quality, climate change's effects on agriculture may reduce crop yields. Impacts of climate change make it more difficult for agriculture to provide for human needs. Global climate change is causing the consequences, which are unevenly spread throughout the planet due to variations in temperature, precipitation, and atmospheric carbon dioxide levels (Pauline et al.;2016).

Areas that are appropriate for farming will change as a result of temperature and weather changes. According to the present forecast, temperatures will rise and precipitation will fall across the Middle East, Africa, Australia, Southwest United States, and Southern Europe, which are all arid and semi-arid regions. Additionally, the projected moderate temperature increase (1-2 °C) anticipated to take place during the first half of the century will have a negative impact on crop yields in tropical countries. Crop yields are expected to decline across the board in the second part of the century, including Canada and the northern United States.

Many common crops are very heat-sensitive; for example, soybean seedlings die at temperatures over 36 °C, and maize pollen becomes lifeless.

In several places of the world, especially Europe, heat waves that are likely related to climate change significantly decreased average yield. More crop failures in August led to an increase in food prices around the world. Governments and food firms were forced to release stored inventories because the output of wheat, rice, and maize was unable to keep up with demand. The CO₂ fertilisation effect, also known as the carbon fertilisation effect, increases photosynthesis while decreasing leaf transpiration in plants.

Both processes are caused by higher levels of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere. The effect of carbon fertilisation varies depending on plant species, air and soil temperature, and water and nutrient availability. The carbon fertilisation effect may boost net primary productivity (NPP). However, data suggests that increased rates of photosynthesis in plants as a result of CO₂ fertilisation do not immediately improve all plant growth and consequently carbon storage. Carbon fertilisation has been reported to be responsible for 44% of the growth in gross primary production (GPP) since the 2000s. To investigate and forecast, Earth System Models, Land System Models, and Dynamic Global Vegetation Models are used (Yanda et al.;2021).

Changes in atmospheric carbon dioxide may affect the nutritional content of some crops, such as wheat, which contains less protein and fewer minerals. The nutritional content of C3 plants (such as wheat, oats, and rice) is severely jeopardised: decreased amounts of protein and minerals (such as zinc and iron) are expected. Protein, iron, and zinc content in popular food crops could be reduced by 3 to 17%. Infections already account for 10-16% of world crop, and this figure is expected to climb as plants become more vulnerable to pests and infections.

Warmer temperatures can boost an insect population's metabolic rate and number of breeding cycles. Insects that formerly had just two breeding cycles each year could obtain an extra cycle if warm growing seasons prolong, resulting in a population explosion. Insect populations are more likely to alter dramatically in temperate areas and higher latitudes. Some bug species will reproduce more quickly because they are more adapted to such shifts in conditions. *Spodoptera frugiperda*, or autumn armyworm, is a very invasive plant pest that has recently spread to Sub-Saharan African countries. Climate change

is linked to the development of this plant pest, as specialists confirm that climate change is bringing more agricultural pests to Africa, and it is estimated that these extremely invasive crop pests will spread to other regions of the world due to their high adaptability to varied settings.

The autumn armyworm can cause extensive damage to crops, particularly maize, reducing agricultural productivity. Climate change has the potential to enhance the amount of arable land by decreasing the amount of frozen land. According to a 2005 study, the average temperature in Siberia has risen by 3x since 1960 (far faster than the rest of the world needs to be updated. However, assessments on the impact of global warming on Russian agriculture reveal contradictory likely effects although they anticipate a northward extension of farmable lands, they also warn of potential productivity losses and increased drought risk.

Warmer air temperatures recorded in recent decades are likely to result in a more active hydrological cycle, including more intense rainfall events. Erosion and soil degradation are more likely. Global warming would also have an impact on soil fertility.

Anthropogenic influences can cause increased erosion in agricultural landscapes, resulting in losses of up to 22% of soil carbon in 50 years. Soils will warm as a result of climate change. As a result, the size of the soil microbial population could expand by 40-150%. Warmer conditions would favour the growth of some bacteria species, altering the composition of the bacterial population. Elevated CO₂ levels would accelerate plant and soil microbial development, delaying the soil carbon cycle and favouring oligotrophs, which are slower-growing and more diverse. Flowering times have gotten earlier as a result of global warming, and early blooms can endanger the plant's life and reproduction. Early flowering raises the danger of frost damage in some plant species and causes 'mismatches' in plant blossoming and pollinator interaction. Around 70% of the world's most produced crop species rely to some extent on insect pollination, accounting for approximately 9% of agricultural production and contributing an estimated €153 billion to the global economy. Furthermore, milder winter temperatures induce many flowering plants to bloom, because plants require stimulation to flower, which is generally

provided by a long winter frost. A plant cannot reproduce if it does not flower. However, if winters continue to get milder, plants may not get cold enough to experience the benefits.

CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE

Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) (or climate resilient agriculture) is an integrated approach to managing landscapes to help adapt agricultural methods, livestock and crops to the effects of climate change and, where possible, counteract it by reducing greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture, at the same time taking into account the growing world population to ensure food security. Thus, the emphasis is not simply on carbon farming or sustainable agriculture, but also on increasing agricultural productivity. "CSA is in line with FAO's vision for Sustainable

Food and Agriculture and supports FAO's goal to make agriculture, forestry and fisheries more productive and more sustainable". CSA has three pillars: increasing agricultural productivity and incomes; adapting and building resilience to climate change; and reducing or removing greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture. CSA lists different actions to counter the future challenges for crops and plants. With respect to rising temperatures and heat stress, e.g., CSA recommends the production of heat tolerant crop varieties, mulching, water management, shade house, boundary trees and appropriate housing and spacing for cattle (Kideghesho ;2015). There are attempts to mainstream CSA into core government policies, expenditures and planning frameworks. In order for CSA policies to be effective, they must be able to contribute to broader economic growth, the sustainable development goals and poverty reduction. They must also be integrated with disaster risk management strategies, actions, and social safety net programmes.

CONCLUSION:

Climate change is posing significant challenges to agriculture, threatening food security, livelihoods, and the overall sustainability of the sector. Extreme weather events, rising temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns, and the spread of pests and diseases are all impacting crop and livestock production. To mitigate these adverse effects, a combination of adaptation and mitigation measures is essential (Joseph, 2015). Sustainable agricultural practices, access to climate information, rural in-

frastructure development, and financial support can help build resilience in the agriculture sector and secure food production in the face of a changing climate. Addressing climate change's impact on agriculture requires collective efforts from governments, farmers, researchers, and the private sector to ensure a sustainable and food-secure future Agriculture plays a significant role in climate change, both as a contributor to greenhouse gas emissions and as a sector vulnerable to the impacts of a changing climate. In this essay, we will delve into the various aspects of agriculture's role in climate change, including its contributions to greenhouse gas emissions, its susceptibility to climate impacts, and potential mitigation and adaptation strategies (Ekpo et al. ;2012).

REFERENCES:

- Bailey, D., and Mouton, J. (1998).**Methods of Social Science Research. London: The free press Collier Macmillan Publisher, 25.
- Charles, R. L., Munishi, P. K. T., and Nzunda, E. F. (2013).** Agroforestry as adaptation strategy under climate change in Mwanga District, Kilimanjaro, Tanzania. *Int. J. Environ. 3*, 29–38.
- Ekpo, F. E., and Asuquo, M. E. (2012).** Agroforestry practice as adaptation tools to climate change hazards in ItuLga, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Glob. J. Hum. Soc. Sci. Geogr. Environ. Geosci. 12*, 27–36.
- FAO (2013).** Climate Smart Agriculture Sourcebook. Rome: FAO.
- Harris, P. G. (2007).** Collective action on climate change: the logic of regime failure. *Nat. Resources J. 47*:195.
- Iloimo, F. M. (2014).** Assessment of Agroforestry Potential in Environmental Conservation and Poverty Reduction in Rural Tanzania: A Case of Lushoto District (Ph.D. Dissertation). University of Dar es Salaam, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.
- Joseph, J. P. (2015).** Effectiveness of Climate Change Mitigation Interventions on Crop Productivity in Morogoro District, Tanzania (Ph.D. dissertation). Department of Development Studies, Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania.
- Kaliba, A. R.M., Verkuil, H.,Mwangi,W.,Mwilawa, A. J. T., Ananda jayasekeram, P., and Moshi, A. J. (1998).** Adoption of Maize Production Technologies in Central Tanzania. Mexico: International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), the United Republic of Tanzania, and the Southern Africa Centre for Cooperation in Agricultural Research (SACCAR).
- Kalineza, H.M.M.,Mdoe,M. S. Y., andMlozi,M. R. S. (1999).** “Factors influencing the adoption of soil conservation technologies in Tanzania: a case study in Gairo,” in Fourth Annual Scientific Conference of the Faculty of Agriculture, 17–19.
- Karwani, G. M., Lulandala, L. L. L., Kimaro, A., and Msigwa, Z. P. (2016).** The role of short rotation coppice technology in fuel wood supply in Rungwe district, Tanzania. *Int. J. Agri. Res. Innov. Technol. 6*, 41–46.
- Kashaigili, J. J., Mbilinyi, B. P., McCartney, M. and Mwanukuzi, F. L. (2006).** Dynamics of Usangu Plains Wetlands: use of remote sensing and GIS as management decision tools. *Phys. Chem. Earth 31*:969975.
- Kideghesho, J. R. (2015).** Realities on Deforestation in Tanzania Trends, Drivers, Implications and the Way Forward. Precious Forests—precious Earth. Rijeka: Intech Open Science/Open Minds, 21–47.
- Kifle, T. (2008)** Africa hit hardest by Global Warming despite its low Greenhouse Gas Emissions. Bremen: Institut für Weltwirtschaft und Internationales Management, Universität Bremen.
- Kilawe, C. J. (2016).** Intensification of Shifting Cultivation in Tanzania: Degree, Drivers and Effects on Vegetation and Soils (Ph.D. dissertation). Department of Geosciences and Natural Resource Management, Faculty of Science, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Lasco, R. D., Delfino, R. J. P., Catacutan, D. C., Simelton, E. S., and Wilson, D. M. (2014).** Climate risk adaptation by smallholder farmers: the roles of trees and agroforestry. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain. 6*, 83-88.
- Lipper, L., Thornton, P., Campbell, B. M., Baedeker, T., Braimoh, A., Bwalya, M., et al. (2014).** Climate-smart agriculture for food security. *Nat. Climate Change 4*:1068.
- Liwenga, E. T. (2003).** Food Insecurity and Coping Strategies in Semiarid Areas: the Case of Mvumi in Central Tanzania (Ph.D dissertation). Almqvist and Wiksell International, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Maduka, S. M. (2007).** Role of Agroforestry Products in Household Income and Poverty Reduction in Semi-Arid Areas of Misungwi District, Mwanza Tanzania (Ph.D. dissertation). Department of Ecosystems and Conservation, Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania.
- Magreth, S., and Bushesha, P. M. (2017).** Potentials of the forest resources in adaptation to climate variability and change in the North Nguu Mountain Block. *Int. J. Environ. Protect. Policy 4*, 178–186.
- Mahenge, J. (2014).** Comparative Economic Analysis of Conservation and Conventional Agricultural Practices in Southern Uluguru Mountains, Morogoro, Tanzania (Ph.D. dissertation). Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania.
- Mjata, P. J. (2015).** The Impact of Climate Change on Rural Livelihoods in the North Nguu Mountains in Kilindi District, Tanzania (Ph.D. dissertation). The Open University of Tan-

zania, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.

Mngumi, J. W. (2016). Perceptions of Climate Change, Environmental Variability and the Role of Agricultural Adaptation Strategies by Small-Scale Farmers in Africa: The Case of Mwanga District in Northern Tanzania (Ph.D. dissertation). University of Glasgow, Glasgow, Scotland.

Namwata, B. M., Masanyiwa, Z. S., and Mzirai, O. B. (2012). Productivity of the agroforestry systems and its contribution to household income among farmers in Lushoto District, Tanzania. *Int. J. Phys. Soc. Sci.* 2, 369–392.

Ndaki, P. M. (2014). Climate Change Adaptation for Smallholder Farmers in Rural Communities: The Case of Mkomazi Sub-Catchment, Tanzania (Ph.D. dissertation). Oldenburg-Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, Oldenburg, Germany.

Nguyen, Q., Hoang, M. H., Öborn, I., and van Noordwijk, M. (2013). Multipurpose agroforestry as a climate change resiliency option for farmers: an example of local adaptation in Vietnam. *Climatic Change* 117, 241–257.

Nyasimi, M., Kimeli, P., Sayula, G., Radeny, M., Kinyangi, J., and Mungai, C. (2017). Adoption and dissemination pathways for climate-smart agriculture technologies and practices for climate-resilient livelihoods in Lushoto, North-east Tanzania. *Climate* 5:63.

O'Neill, B. C., Oppenheimer, M., Warren, R., Hallegatte, S., Kopp, R. E., Pörtner, H. O., et al. (2017). IPCC reasons for concern regarding climate change risks. *Nat. Climate Change* 7, 28–37. doi: 10.1038/nclimate3179

Paavola, J. (2008). Livelihoods, vulnerability and adaptation to climate change in Morogoro, Tanzania. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 11, 642–654.

Pauline, N., and Grab, S. (2018). Whose knowledge matters in climate change adaptation? Perceived and measured rainfall trends during the last half century in south-western Tanzania. *Singapore J. Trop. Geogr.* 39, 266–280.

Pauline, N. M. (2015). Living With Climate Variability and Change: Lessons From Tanzania (Ph.D. dissertation). Johannesburg: Faculty of Science, University of the Witwatersrand.

Pauline, N. M., Vogel, C., Grab, S., and Liwenga, E. T. (2017). Smallholder farmers in the Great Ruaha River sub-Basin of Tanzania: coping or adapting to rainfall variability? *Climate Dev.* 9, 217–230.

Pye-Smith, C. (2010). A Rural Revival in Tanzania: How Agroforestry Is Helping Farmers to Restore the Woodlands in Shinyanga Region. Nairobi: World Agroforestry Centre.

Rahman, S. A. (2017). Incorporation of Trees in Smallholder Land Use Systems: Farm Characteristics, Rates of Return and Policy Issues Influencing Farmer Adoption (Ph.D. dissertation). Department of Food and Resource Economics, Faculty of Science, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark.

Ramadhani, T., Otsyina, R., and Franzel, S. (2002). Improving household incomes and reducing deforestation using rotational woodlots in Tabora district, Tanzania. *Agri. Eco-*

syst. Environ. 89, 229–239.

Rowhani, P., Lobell, D. B., Linderman, M., and Ramanakutty, N. (2011). Climate variability and crop production in Tanzania. *Agric. Forest Meteorol.* 151, 449–460.

Ruboya, A. A. (2013). Effects of Rotational Woodlots on Households' Livelihood in Meatu District, Tanzania (Doctoral dissertation). Sokoine university of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania.

Sage, C. (2013). The interconnected challenges for food security from a food regimes perspective: energy, climate and malconsumption. *J. Rural Stud.* 29, 71–80. doi: 10.1016/j.jrurstud.2012.02.005

Schroth, G. (ed.). (2004). Agroforestry and Biodiversity Conservation in Tropical Landscapes. Island Press.

Shalli, M. S. (2003). Contribution of Agroforestry against Rural Household Food Security in Kibaha District, Coast Region (Ph.D. dissertation). Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania.

Shilabu, M. D. T. (2008). The Contribution of Agroforestry to Household Food Security and Income Generation in Maswa District, Shinyanga Region (Ph.D. dissertation). Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania.

Thenya, T. (2001). Challenges of Conservation of Dryland Shallow Waters. Laikipia: Ewaso Narok Swamp. Thorlakson, T., and Neufeldt, H. (2012). Reducing subsistence farmers' vulnerability to climate change: evaluating the potential contributions of agroforestry in western Kenya. *Agric Food Secur.* 1:15.

Uisso, A. J. (2015). Agroforestry practices, an option for climate change adaptation: a review. *Octa J. Environ. Res.* 3, 219–225.

UNFCCC (2008). Investment and Financial Flows to Address Climate Change: An Update, Vol. 13. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), 1–111.

United Republic of Tanzania (2012). Population and Housing Census by Sex and Number of Households. Tanzania. Available online at: <http://www.nbs.go.tz/sense/popu2.php> (accessed August 12, 2017).

Yanda, P. Z., Kangalawe, R. Y., and Sigalla, R. J. (2005). Climatic and Socioeconomic Influences on Malaria and Cholera Risks in the Lake Victoria Region of Tanzania. AIACC Working Papers.

Yanda, P. Z., and Mubaya, C. P. (2011). Managing a Changing Climate in Africa: Local Level Vulnerabilities and Adaptation Experiences. Dar es Salaam: African Books Collective.